

The importance of magnetic measurements dovetailed with chemical analysis for the rapid characterization of heavy metal-bearing urban dust load

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Abstract : Major cities of the world are found to be dangerously close to or exceeding the permissible limit of particulate size in inhalable air (grains size $<10\ \mu\text{m}$). However, the cities with high population density and unique environmental conditions are prone to heavy metal contamination that is reflected in the suspended particulate matter. In such cases, metal toxicity in air is monitored on the basis of chemical and/or granulometric analyses requiring expensive instruments and sample preparation technique. Environmental magnetism is a relatively new area of research which uses magnetic properties of the particulate matter to monitor environmental pollution and at the same time it is rapid, quantitative, non-destructive and inexpensive. The present study reflects the effectiveness of magnetic measurements coupled with selective chemical analysis to show the level of heavy metal contamination in parts of Allahabad city, India. The dust samples are collected from road side tree leaves comprising 1052 number of samples during four different sampling periods between January, 2011 and January, 2013 are also analyzed by microscopic, sub-microscopic, chemical, magnetic and XRD techniques. The concentration of Pb, Zn, Ni, Cr and Cd in roadside dust samples of Allahabad is very high and compares well with some of the most polluted locations worldwide. Interestingly, the magnetic susceptibility values of the dust samples (3.1 and $1262 \times 10^{-8}\ \text{m}^3\ \text{kg}^{-1}$) show a positive correlation with heavy metal contents.

Keywords : Magnetic measurements, environmental pollution, heavy metals, road side dust.

Introduction

In recent years the characterization of dust load by magnetic susceptibility measurements as well as geochemical analysis has become a standard approach in aerosol research^{1,2}. The urban dust load is a collective assemblage of varied size particulate matter derived from lithogenic and/or anthropogenic sources and with or without possible inputs from the cosmogenic sources. The inhalable dust particulate size is an important parameter to evaluate its impact on life forms. Similarly the concentration of heavy metals in the urban dust load is a good indicator of atmospheric pollution vis-à-vis human health³. The magnetic concentrations as well as chemical analysis data show seasonal fluctuations (high in thick winter fog period versus low and small in summer, respectively) due to the variation in seasonal influx of anthropogenic material invariably having magnetic constituents^{4,5}.

The cities of North India are severely affected by fog every year between December and February, and Allahabad city ($25^{\circ}27'33.40''$; $81^{\circ}52'45.47''$), covering an area of about 63 sq. km and a population of near 12

million, is one the fog-prone cities. Although, there are only a handful of industrial units within the city limits still the dust load is significant. Hence, Allahabad city has been chosen for this case study to understand the effectiveness of magnetic measurements coupled with limited chemical analysis to ascertain heavy metal pollution in roadside urban dust load.

Results

The average mineral magnetic measurements of 1052 samples and 40 geochemical data collected over a period of 3 years are summarized in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The magnetic measurements of dust samples collected during the fog, post-monsoon and pre-monsoon phases for 3 years period between 2011 and 2013 show variation in terms of low frequency (LF), high frequency (HF) and mass magnetic susceptibility values (Table 1). The range of average volume magnetic susceptibility values for 1052 samples for LF (0.13 to 67), HF (0.1 to 65.5) and mass magnetic susceptibility (3.1 to $1262 \times 10^{-8}\ \text{m}^3\ \text{kg}^{-1}$) exhibit variation in terms of the type of the

Table 1. Comparison between magnetic parameters such as χ_{LF} values of present study and published values from other countries⁶⁻⁹

Measurements	Units	Range	Mean
LF and HF (Volume magnetic susceptibility, present study)	Dimension less	0.13 to 67 (LF) 0.1 to 65.5 (HF)	6.9 (LF) 6.6 (HF)
χ_{LF} (Mass magnetic susceptibility, present study)	$10^{-8} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$	3.1-1262	194.4
Kim <i>et al.</i> 2007	$10^{-8} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$	-	62.00
Ovaia <i>et al.</i> 2012	$10^{-8} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$	-0.21 to -29.62	9.04

Table 2. Comparison of heavy metal elements analyses (values in parts per million) of selected leaf dust samples (average of 40 samples in the present study) with other countries⁶⁻⁹ carried out by ICP-MS technique is summarized

Sample details	Pb	Cd	Cr	Zn	Ni
Present study	13-129	0.3-1.96	13-172	95-320	28-172
Kim <i>et al.</i> 2007	61-389	-	31-107	242-393	-
Wei <i>et al.</i> 2009	13-99	0.11-14	20.2-174	69-846	-
Nazzal <i>et al.</i> 2013	32.5-378	0.46-0.95	57.3-558	-	16-327
Germade <i>et al.</i> 2014	-	0.03-0.19	-	-	0.69-3.00

magnetic phase(s) and its modal concentration. Based on XRD data, the dust samples are found to comprise quartz, feldspar, magnetite, gypsum, biotite mica and illite, predominantly and their presence is supported by the magnetic susceptibility values. In these samples, quartz-rich samples have the lowest susceptibility values and magnetite-rich have the highest. Based on observed magnetic susceptibility variations, forty representative road dust samples collected from parts of Allahabad city were analyzed for Cd, Cr, Ni, Pb and Zn content using ICP-MS technique. Their concentration is in the ppm range (Table 2) and shows variation in space and time. The heavy metal content increases during the fog period compared to post-monsoon and pre-monsoon (least polluted). The maximum concentration of heavy metals observed in dust samples is that of Zn (95-320 ppm) and the content of Cd is the least (0.3-1.96 ppm).

Discussions

It is interesting to note that despite having relatively less number of industries and comparatively low traffic volume, the susceptibility values of the particulate matters in all sampling periods are much higher than industrial cities like Seoul, Korea⁶ and Madrid, Spain⁷ and

similarly heavy metals values are also higher (Fig. 1) compared to some developed countries like China⁸ and Canada⁹. In Allahabad city, a positive correlation between magnetic susceptibility data and chemical constituents of the dust load has been established. In the present study the Pb concentration is high possibly derived from anthropogenic sources (like vehicular source and industrial units like thermal power plants). The high concentration of Cr is attributed to the emissions of chromium-based automotive catalytic converters used in vehicles. High concentration of Zn in the environment possibly

Fig. 1. Trace elements analyses (values in parts per million) of 40 selected leaf dust samples (present study) plotted and compared with published results from other countries⁶⁻⁹.

comes from both natural and anthropogenic sources (like vehicular rubber tyres). This study suggests that the increase of vehicular pollution is one of the main reasons for the increase of pollutants in atmospheric dust of Allahabad city. In addition, the emissions from the only major industrial unit (IFFCO; Indian Farmers Fertilizer Co-operative Limited), a thermal power plant situated in

the vicinity of the city at Phulpur also contribute significantly to atmospheric pollution of the city¹⁰.

This finding is also significant since this study shows magnetic susceptibility values are higher than a site-specific threshold. In addition, the present study demonstrates the potential of magnetic susceptibility field mapping for the rapid preliminary site assessment, greatly reducing the scale of subsequent geochemical sampling and analysis. In addition, it is a non-destructive technique and requires samples in mg to gm level which is a boon for leaf dust studies as sample weight is mostly in the milligram range.

Experimental description

The samples of dust particulates per ten dust-loaded tree leaves were collected from 300 sites of Allahabad city from 4 different deciduous trees of *Ficus benghalensis*, *Ficus religiosa*, *Cassia fistula* and *Anthocephalus cadamba*. The magnetic susceptibility was measured using Bartington dual frequency magnetic susceptibility meter (MS2 B, U.K.; Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences, University of Allahabad) and geochemical analyses are carried out using ICP-MS (Perkin-Elmer SCIEX Quadrupole type ELAN DRC-e, Wadia Institute of Himalayan Geology, Dehradun) instrument.

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